

Python in Heliophysics Community Fall 2024 Meeting

Meeting materials are located at <http://pyhc.org/meetings/>

*Meeting recordings can be found on the meeting's web page at
<https://pyhc.org/meetings/fall2024/>*

Table of Contents

Python in Heliophysics Community Fall 2024 Meeting	1
Table of Contents	2
Participants	3
Meeting Overview	4
Core Packages Updates	4
HAPI	4
PlasmaPy	5
SunPy	7
SpacePy	7
pysat	8
Kamodo	8
PySPEDAS	9
Other efforts	10
CLEDB (Alin P)	10
fiasco (Will Barnes)	11
EMToolKit DEM Framework (Joseph Plowman)	12
Space Packet Parser (Gavin Medley)	13
Radiation Belts Analysis and Modeling Library in Python (Sasha Drozdov)	14
PyHC Tech Lead Updates	15
Science Platforms Coordination IHDEA Working Group	15
pyhc-core	16
PyHC Docs Hub	16
PyHC Tech Lead Vision	16
Heliophysics Software Search Interface	17
High-level Overview	17
Metadata Structure Supporting HSSI and Controlled Vocabularies	18
PyHC Tiering Discussion	20
Community Ideas for Levels	20
Tier requirements/benefits	22
PyHC Requirements and the HSSI	27
Interoperability within PyHC	34
PHEP Issues Revisit	38
PHEPs 2 and 3 Voting	40
Next Steps	40
References	41
Final agenda	42

Participants

54 individuals registered to participate in the hybrid Fall 2024 meeting via the meeting's Google sign up form. Of those 54 people, approximately 10-15 participants attended in-person, with the rest participating via the Zoom. Meeting participants' home institutions (as indicated by responses to the Google sign up form) included the following:

- Lockheed Martin Space and Astrophysical Laboratory
- Embry Riddle Aeronautical University
- Naval Research Laboratory (NRL)
- University of Miami
- Laboratory for Atmospheric and Space Physics (LASP)
- University of Colorado Boulder
- NASA Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC)
- NASA GSFC Heliophysics Digital Resource Library (HDRL)
- UC Berkeley Space Sciences Lab
- Johns Hopkins University Applied Physics Lab (JHU APL)
- American University
- Southwest Research Institute
- University of New Hampshire
- Aperio Software
- National Solar Observatory (NSO)
- European Space Agency (ESA)
- NSF National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) High Altitude Observatory (HAO)
- University of Texas at Arlington
- Smithsonian Astrophysical observatory
- University of Bergen, Norway
- University of Edinburgh, UK
- National University of Engineering
- University of Arizona
- Utica University
- Universidad Nacional de Ingeniería
- Center for Astrophysics | Harvard & Smithsonian
- George Mason University
- National University of Engineering
- Community Cordinated Modeling Center (CCMC)
- University of Turku (Finland)
- NASA Marshall Space Flight Center (MSFC)
- NASA Space Physics Data Facility (SPDF)
- Egypt-Japan University of Science and Technology
- New Jersey Institute of Technology
- University of Maryland
- Institute of Astronomy and National Astronomical Observatory BAS
- University of California, Los Angeles

- Georgia State University

Meeting Overview

Core Packages Updates

To kick off the fall 2025 meeting, core package developers presented relevant updates since the spring 2024 bi-annual meeting. Below are notes on those presentations.

HAPI

The presentation began with a quick overview. HAPI is a specification defining simple access to time series data. Many data servers that are HAPI enabled (e.g., from institutions like NASA, IRAP Plasma Data Center, CU Boulder/LASP, SWARM, ESA/ESAC, etc. - totalling over 10,000 data sets) and several client softwares can read in HAPI data (Python client, PySPEDAS/SPEDAS, MATLAB, IDL, R, Autoplot, TopCat). Making data available through HAPI means anyone using the client softwares can now access that data. More servers in the process of enabling HAPI (you can find the current list on the HAPI Data Explorer website!).

Several updates are coming to the HAPI package. First, they plan to add the ability to advertise linkages between HAPI datasets together. It's nice to know when different datasets are related, e.g., lots of dataset versions at different time resolutions. One HAPI client did this with their server so the client tool could automatically choose the correct resolution depending on what a user wanted to visualize time-wise. The HAPI team is incorporating this now into their main software. Has taken time since the problem can be generalized to various reasons for linking datasets (e.g., file listing with datasets or linking raw data to calibrated data). Second, HAPI is looking into further FAIR compliance. Rebecca Ringuette helped do a scan of HAPI software to provide feedback. The HAPI team plans to add a license keyword and provenance. Lastly, there are several other updates in the pipeline: 1) HAPI caching mechanism that works with Python client or any language client (poster at AGU to come), 2) HAPI amalgamation/local data serving Python tool (being worked on by Sandy Antunes), and 3) HAPI metadata to SPASE generator tool under way (early on in progress).

There are a few updates that the HAPI would love to do, but the developers simply don't have time themselves to complete. These would greatly benefit from community help, if someone has the time and funding. These include: generic plotting client via adapting of KNMI tool and integration within HelioCloud (using HAPI for cloud-to-cloud data transfers).

HAPI has various adoption initiatives in mind, including adding more datasets (mentioned earlier) and pursuing official designation as an IHDEA standard. There is no official process yet for this, but will likely be patterned after the IVOA process.

The presentation finished with an interoperability proposal to the PyHC: consider creating a common data model for time series data. The end goal is to make it so that tools don't need any information on data sources in order to work with data. See Figs 1 and 2 for more information on this.

PyHC Needs a Common Data Model for Time Series

- interoperability requires "sameness layer"

- for analysis and plotting code, this is an internal data model

Fig 1: HAPI's interoperability proposition to PyHC

Common Data Model for Time Series

- data model isolates data sources from analysis code
- plotting tools become truly re-usable
- data model can be language agnostic, but it needs a **single python expression**; other codes then import
- requires an agreement on how to represent time!
- also needs agreement on data array storage
- needs to have a flexible metadata capability
- HAPI is *not* this model – HAPI is more like a transport protocol, so it is one data source and will be adapted into the common model like everything else.

Fig 2: a further explanation of the common data model for time series

PlasmaPy

Several general updates were given for PlasmaPy including the release of v2024.10.0 in October of 2024. The biggest change here was a removal of any numba dependency, resulting in quicker Python 3.13 support. Other changes in v2024.10.0 included:

- Updated/expanded contributor guide in prep for summer school
- Switched to src/ layout recommended by Python packaging guide
- Continuing to improve type hint coverage
- New functionality for high energy density physics
- Switched test runner from tox to Nox (Nox config files are written in Python and more user friendly!)

PlasmaPy members attended the American Physical Society Division of Plasma Physics (APS DPP) meeting. For the past few iterations (2022, 2023, and 2024) PlasmaPy had a booth at the meeting. Thanks to this, developers were able to chat with lots of students and early career folks. At the meeting, Nick Murphy presented the need for workforce development for RSEs. This led Nick to ponder the question: *should we have PyHC booths at Heliophysics conferences?*

PlasmaPy achieved a huge milestone through holding the inaugural PlasmaPy Summer School. This was a sequel to Plasma Hack Weeks from 2021 and 2022. The meeting was held July 29 - August 2, 2024, after the PyHC summer school. Several travel awards were given through NSF, with a focus on supporting early-career individuals (even a few from the PyHC 2024 summer school). The overall theme was about “how to use and contribute to PlasmaPy” (further topics discussed are displayed in Fig 3). Half of the sessions were led by Shauna Gordon-McKeon for general things like how to contribute to GitHub, etc. Nick noted that Shauna would be a good person for PyHC in general to talk with.

Summer school topics

- PlasmaPy’s origin story
- git & GitHub
- astropy.units
- PlasmaPy subpackages: particles, formulary, dispersion
- Psychological safety in code review
- Contributing documentation
- Decorators & type hints (with PlasmaPy applications)
- Unconferences and hack sessions on last day
- Group lunches

Fig 3: PlasmaPy 2024 summer school topics

The success behind this summer school begs the question: *Should PyHC have a summer school that focuses on how to contribute to PyHC packages?* Doing so would help with workforce development of helio research software engineers, albeit requiring a lot of work on the planning committee’s part. Further, PyHC would need to consider who it would be targeting -

scientists? RSEs? Both are probably likely, and it would behoove PyHC to blur the line between users and contributors. Finally, if PyHC goes through with this idea in the future, it could reduce lift by bringing in external trainers (e.g., Shauna), or leveraging existing resources (US-RSE, INTERSECT, NASA TOPS, pyOpenSci, etc.).

Nick Murphy ended the PlasmaPy talk with comments on funding. PlasmaPy's current NSF CSSI award concludes in a few months. A renewal proposal is due December 2nd. Including in PlasmaPy summer schools in 2026, 2028, and 2030. Also looking into: NASA HTM, NASA OSTFL, DOE opportunities.

SunPy

Updates for SunPy include that v6.0 was released in June 2024. Lots of improvements therein. 16 new contributors for this release. Also, v6.1 coming December 2024. The biggest improvements to come therein are support for the Helioprojective Radial coordinate frame and adding support for loading Map and Timeseries directly from URLs (e.g., S3) with fsspec. Further improvements to the OpenAstronomy packaging guide² and automated templating (where essentially the OpenAstronomy and SunPy specific functionality makes up the SunPy package template) were conducted. Third, there was a major overhaul of SunPy Project Governance, heavily inspired by Astropy. Previously, there was a self-electing board who appointed key personnel like the Lead Developer (in place around 2012). Now, there exists a self-electing Project custodians based on a positive record of contribution to the project, 3-person Steering Committee (elected by the custodians), and Self-Electing Advisory Board (still a work-in-progress). Steering Committee Elected: Stuart Mumford, Laura Hayes and Albert Shih.

For funding, SunPy was recently awarded ROSES OSTFL 2024 funding (co-PIs: Albert Shih, Will Barnes, Stuart Mumford, Sam Badman, and Kris Cooper). Plans for this grant include project-wide documentation improvements (including cross-project examples), new features and improvements to sunkit-spex and sunkit-magex, as well as general SunPy maintenance. Vision for long-term SunPy maintenance? Currently, there are not many other paths to sustainability of packages like SunPy except continued grant funding. An ongoing challenge. Numfocus is helping SunPy with it.

SpacePy

SpacePy released v0.6.0 in April 2024. This included a conversion to/from Astropy quantities and Pandas, and pybats updates - calculate IMF clock angle, calculate Perreault and Akasofu (1978) epsilon. v0.7.0 was released in November 2024, just before this fall meeting. v0.7.0 essentially spent out a one-year support grant from NASA. Mostly undergraduate work. Several fixes, including deprecations on numpy 2.x and Python 3.13 (supporting now Python 3.7-3.13). Also, ripped out f2py to remove build dependency on numpy, to the end of things still working when a new version of Python comes out. With f2py removal, SpacePy can now increase the

cadence of releases. Further, v0.7.0 increased maturity of documentation and tests through a restructured Sphinx doc overhaul and test coverage increased on 5 modules.

What does the future horizon look like for SpacePy? The package is currently seeking sustainability through writing proposals (e.g., OSTFL). SpacePy is actively trying to find ways to support past one-year installments to keep momentum going for the various efforts. Many of Jon Niehof's current students are seniors, so he is seeking funding for freshman and sophomores to increase sustainability (with a focus on increasing representation). Next, SpacePy will slowly incorporate more of conda-forge (switching building to conda-forge instead of default, packaging NASA CDF to avoid bundling, and finish with build rules for SpacePy). Other to-dos include: adapting between PyHC data objects (Jon Vandegriff is the PI, but progress has been delayed due to SpacePy updates), working on cloud file support, and working through 3D SWMF support (in pybats).

pysat

pysat released a new version 3.2.1. This included two bug fixes, updated for deprecations, and transitioned to Scientific Python Ecosystem Coordination (SPEC) 0 testing limits from NEP29. pysatNASA 0.0.6 was released in October 2024, which added six new supported instruments, nine bug fixes, and four new features (allow files to be unzipped after download, new concatenation methods for different data types, new cleaning routines, etc.). Also, pysatSpaceWeather package has a release coming up this month, and pysat is currently working on some clean-up and updates on pysatMissions, pysatSeasons, and pysatCDAAC.

Current stable releases for the pysat suite are as follows:

- Pysat: v3.2.1 (October 2024)
- pysatNASA: v0.0.6 (October 2024)
- pysatSpaceWeather: v0.2.0 (August 2024)
- pysatSeasons: v0.2.0 (September 2022)
- pysatMadrigal: v0.2.0 (March 2024)
- pysatCDAAC: v0.0.4 (August 2023)

Kamodo

Kamodo recently added a Versatile Electron Radiation Belt (VERB) model reader (See Fig 4), which is a new prototype Fortran to Python interface (from Fortran code call into Kamodo in Python, send a query and interoperate a value), a Tsyganenko tool (TS05), updated web interface (Kamodo on the web) to visualizations of CCMC Run-on-Request model runs, and addressed plenty of small bug fixes and improvements.

VERB:

Versatile Electron Radiation Belt

- The VERB code is a diffusion model, which simulates the dynamics of particles in multi-dimensional space.
- Coordinate systems dimensions include L-shell, adiabatic invariants, and pitch-angles
- These dimensions require unique interpolation methods to function in Kamodo and support functions such as satellite flythrough.
- Development via sole-source grant by Alexander (Sasha) Drozdov and Dmitri Kondrashov included:
 - VERB model reader, documentation, validation notebook, plotting example notebook, unit testing

Fig 4: VERB model information

Future plans for Kamodo include: 1) bringing Python support up to version 3.12 (currently only go up to 3.10), 2) updating documentation and unit testing, 3) adding field line tracing functionality (a general tool that will work with all Kamodo supported models), 4) pip/conda-forge updates if and only if there's a way to include C code in a pip upgrade (can't update pip until that is the case - Jon Niehof indicated that he may be able to help with this!), and 5) updating Kamodo CCMC documentation so broken examples will be fixed and work properly.

PySPEDAS

This presentation started with a quick overview. PySPEDAS is the successor to IDL SPEDAS, ported into Python. Loads data into "tplot variables" (containers for time series data and metadata). It is based in matplotlib, and the current versions are: PySPEDAS v1.7.0 (November 2024) and pyplot-mpl-temp v2.2.50 (November 2024).

PySPEDAS has pushed out several new updates. First, developers worked on environment requirements: PySPEDAS now supports numpy 2.0 and Python versions 3.9 - 3.12. Upstream package dependencies (e.g., netCDF4) are not cleanly installable under Python version 3.13 yet. Secondly, PySPEDAS improved plotting capabilities to include more plot options, better handling of "pseudo-variables" (displaying multiple tplot variables in a single panel), better handling of plots with symbols and error bars, and greatly reduced memory consumption and rendering time for spectrogram plots. Lastly, other updates included 1) improved analysis tools for better NaN value handling, fixed bugs in code, and contributed bug fixes to upstream magnetic field modeling library (geopack), 2) updates on the load routines and CDF reading by fixing some bugs, adding load routines for more geomagnetic indices, and relaxed some ISTP

compliance checks to allow loading certain ERG and Cluster datasets, 3) resolved deprecations through changing some calls to upstream libraries (numpy, astropy, scipy, and pandas) that were flagged as deprecated, 4) efforts on packaging and organization through alignment with pyOpenSci recommendations, as well as namespace reorganization, 5) general documentation updates to flesh out PySPEDAS and pyplot readthedocs pages (and better release notes for past PySPEDAS releases), and 6) completed general quality analysis and testing improvements (achieved 90% test coverage milestone for PySPEDAS)!

The biggest upcoming change is the PySPEDAS 2.0.0 is coming soon! This version will include breaking changes, hence the major release bump. In v2.0.0, PySPEDAS plans to completely absorb pyplot-mpl-temp package, while retiring older pyplot and pyplot-mpl-temp packages, add backward compatibility hacks for making mission-specific modules available directly under PySPEDAS, and update code examples and tutorial presentations and notebooks based on the new namespace organization. A current rough draft of v2.0.0 migration guide is available on readthedocs³. Other planned updates include:

- Migrating from setuptools to PDM as backend build system.
- Publishing PySPEDAS to conda-forge (dependent on upstream dependencies, especially the geopack package).
- Implementing field line tracing routines using models from geopack.
- Including better support for non time series plots (e.g., orbit plots, field line plots, region of interest boundaries).

Other efforts

CLEDB (Alin P)

The Coronal Line Emission DataBase (CLEDB) Inversion algorithm is a self-described “newbie” attempt to develop heliophysics analysis software. CLEDB is a mostly open-source Python code (+90%), parallelized, coronal spectropolarimetry package. This is currently available only as a GitHub repository (<https://github.com/arparaschiv/solar-coronal-inversion>). Funding sources include the NSO Community Science Program, an HAO fellowship, DKIST, and a NASA HTM grant. This package aims to enable the community to interpret novel DKIST Cryo-NIRSP and MLSL uCoMP observations. CLEDB has a dedicated documentation and tutorial page available at: <https://cledb.readthedocs.io/>.

The problem at hand is too complicated to solve analytically. Therefore, CLEDB does forward calculations, builds databases of potential solutions that match observations, and then matches those bases to the solutions at the end (Fig 5). The original setup of the CLEDB atomic database was updated to leverage PyCELP (<https://github.com/tschad/pycelp>), a novel, Python-based spectral synthesis code that allow for great calculation flexibility (developed by Tom Schad and Gabriel Dima). This, and other changes, resulted in an algorithm that runs much faster than before.

The CLEDB pipeline setup

Fig 5: Diagram of CLEDB software flow

The package is currently compatible with 8 out of 15 PyHC community code standards. The code is partly compatible with another three standards (5, 17, and 14), although their implementation in the code base is either not complete, or the current code is not fully compatible with the suggested guidelines. Four standards still need to be enabled (1, 3, 9, and 15). Short-term upcoming work will focus on module unit testing, packaging, and moving to regular code releases.

New science and instrument support capabilities are planned: disambiguation of coronal vector magnetograms and enabling analysis software support for novel DKIST Cryo-NIRSP, DL-NIRSP, uCoMP, and COSMO. Further, CLEDB is committed to adhering to the PyHC code standards and working with the community towards including CLEDB in the PyHC universe. The question was posed: “how does one inexperienced developer get in contact with the relevant people in the community?” Any input on how to proceed and tips and tricks pertaining to such tasks are appreciated.

fiasco (Will Barnes)

Much of this presentation focused on the background of the reasoning behind the fiasco package and demoing its current uses. The fiasco software package was inspired by the object-oriented design of ChiantiPy⁴ (a pure Python package that leverages the CHIANTI atomic database to make calculations of astro-physical spectra). The CHIANTI atomic database grew out of efforts in the early 90s to make atomic data and software freely and publicly available. Its v1.0 was released in 1996, v11 in 2024. The database consists of a large (~1.5 GB) collection of plain text files. Software to leverage it was written in IDL. This software parses the database,

computes derived quantities, as well as some GUI capabilities. However, this lacked automated tests, open development, and backwards compatibility. The software is also tied to the version of the database it works with. ChiantiPy has been developed since approximately 2006 to address the CHIANTI database software issues.

ChiantiPy, however, still doesn't quite meet the software standards expected within PyHC. Thus, Will Barnes created a new package, `fiasco`⁵, around 2017 as a graduate student. The first version, v0.1, was not released until January 2023, however. The package is now at v0.3, released in September 2024. The package is developed openly on GitHub, with automated testing on GitHub Actions and documentation on `readthedocs`⁶. `fiasco` uses `astropy.units` everywhere (inputs and outputs), `plamapy.particles` for parsing ion/element labeling, and plain text database files parsed into a single HDF5 database.

The building block of `fiasco` is the ion object. The database is organized into several subdirectories, with a subdirectory for every ion in the database (and data attached to that ion). See Fig 6 for an example of an implementation within `fiasco`. The presentation continued with further examples of combining ion objects together to create elements.

Compared to the beginnings of this package, it is now available on PyPI, has more features (continuum calculations and support for new data formats in CHIANTI releases), systematic comparisons with IDL code to keep up-to-date, better documentation, and the contributor community has grown. The project is now formally associated with the CHIANTI team, and has a dedicated funding source (ISFM program at NASA GSFC). Future work includes support for v9, v10 of CHIANTI database, as well as better integration with `PlasmaPy`.

```
1 import fiasco
2 import astropy.units as u
3 temperature = 10*np.arange(4,8,0.01)*u.K
4 fe_14 = fiasco.Ion('Fe XIV', temperature)
5 fe_14

1 print(fe_14.ion_name_roman)
2 print(fe_14.element_name)
3 print(fe_14.ip.to('eV'))
4 print(fe_14.abundance)
1 fe_14[0]
```

```
CHIANTI Database Ion
-----
Name: Fe 14
Element: iron (26)
Charge: +13
Number of Levels: 739
Number of Transitions: 42667

Temperature range: [0.010 MK, 97.724 MK]

HDF5 Database:
/Users/wtbarnes/Documents/projects/chianti/database/CHIANTI_v8.0.7/dbase.h5
Using Datasets:
  ioneq: chianti
  abundance: sun_coronal_1992_feldman_ext

Fe XIV
iron
392.1620196442125 eV
0.0001258925411794166

Level: 1
Configuration: 3s2.3p
Orbital Angular Momentum: P
Energy: 0.0 eV
```

Fig 6: implementation example within `fiasco` software

EMToolKit DEM Framework (Joseph Plowman)

For the past few years, `EMToolKit`⁷, a Python DEM framework, has been in development. This effort has been funded by NASA. The basic pieces are now largely complete, and the current funding round finished. For context, EUV observations (Joe gave an example of AIA 335 “showing as a temperature of about 2.5 million Kelvin”) respond to the distribution of density

squared as a function of temperature, integrated over the line of sight. This quantity is the Differential Emission Measure, or DEM. DEMs encapsulate all these observations and can tell us about their coronal plasma column.

Various algorithms exist now, mostly in IDL, that calculate DEMs and have differing formats for inputs and outputs. EMToolKit ports some of these standard DEM algorithms into Python with standardized interfaces and visualization tools. The package doesn't modify algorithms, but adds wrappers to put data and DEMs in standard representation (based on NDCube). Thus, with a wrapper, any DEM/data can be put into EMToolKit (see Fig 7).

As mentioned previously, the current funding round is finished. Joe indicated that he intends to seek out continued funding. Future updates would include adding error estimation, figure export, and time series plots. It's unsure if sporadic, long-term NASA grants is the most viable option, or if the package is self-sustaining enough to become a community project.

Fig 7: EMToolKit diagram

Space Packet Parser (Gavin Medley)

This package has previously been presented to the PyHC in its early stages.

Space Packet Parser^{8,9} is a CCSDS telemetry decoder. It uses an XTCE (XML Telemetry and Command Exchange format) document for configuration, can handle complex packets, is actively developed at LASP, and is used on multiple large missions (IMAP, Libera, MMS, CLARREO Pathfinder). It has a roadmap for new features and easier packet decoding.

Since the last presentation, the development team has implemented several changes. They added StringDataEncoding parsing to match the XTCE spec, raw data for strings and binary blobs are returned as bytes objects, the CCSDSPacket class is now a subclass of dict (enabling easier lookup of items), added MIL-1750A float encoding, and finally, added time data types

(with contributions from Caden Gobat at SwRI). The rest of 2024, the development team will work on: 1) direct return of Xarray DataSet object from the parser, 2) CLI tools for inspecting packet files and packets within them, 3) CSV to XTCE conversion tool (exact CSV spec TBD), and continuation packet support.

Radiation Belts Analysis and Modeling Library in Python (Sasha Drozdov)

This was an update presentation for an existing NASA HTM grant awarded project, Radiation Belts Analysis and Modeling Library in Python (rbamlib)^{10,11}. rbamlib is a lightweight, open-source Python library for the analysis and modeling of radiation belts. It is designed to provide an open framework for the contribution enabling the best practices of open science. The library itself provides essential functionalities for radiation belt studies, with detailed documentation. This includes system properties calculations, empirical model collections, and modeling support. Planned key features for rbamlib included: 1) system properties (Adiabatic invariants transformation, drift velocities, phase space density, and motion periods calculation, adaptable for different planets), 2) empirical models collection (radial diffusion coefficients, lifetimes, local diffusion coefficients scaling, plasma densities, etc.), and 3) modeling support (conversion between simulation grids, boundary and initial condition characteristics, adiabatic transformation of boundary scaling factors).

As for the library's current status, the conv (conversion) package was implemented. It provides tools for the conversion between various physical quantities pertinent to particle physics, including adiabatic invariants. The models package is partially implemented. It is a collection of scientific models for space physics research. Currently implemented sub-packages include:

- lpp: Plasmapause location models
- mp : Magnetopause location models, and
- dip : Dipole field model.

The models package also includes templates for the unimplemented (empty) functions for future development. Additionally, unittests were developed (79 tests), there's now automatic generation of the Sphinx documentation (inspired by PlasmaPy), a comprehensive developer contribution guide was written, and the package has been tested and the first version is published in PyPI. The first version of the library is already used in Kamodo, and the library functionality was demonstrated at GFZ, Potsdam.

Future plans include finishing the implementation of the models and function (e.g., pitch-angle distribution and isotropic boundary) and automatic testing via GitHub actions. However, Sasha listed a few challenges that the project has faced: community engagement (lack of places to showcase the package), automatic package deployment was originally desired but requires further consideration, and how to include data with some functions. Open contributions are welcomed.

PyHC Tech Lead Updates

Shawn Polson, the PyHC Tech Lead, presented an update on his current work, all of which is aimed to unify PyHC packages and everything that PyHC does. The first half of the talk focused on the new IHDEA working group, Science Platforms Coordination. This same talk was presented at DASH 2024 for those who attended. Other parts of the talk included updates on side projects (pyhc-core and PyHC Docs Hub), his overall vision for PyHC and a discussion of that.

Science Platforms Coordination IHDEA Working Group

The Science Platforms Coordination working group aims to develop international standard software computing environments for Heliophysics (not just limited to PyHC). It is chaired by Shawn, as well as Jan Reerink (ESA), with several other members within the Heliophysics software community. Since its first kick off meeting in October 2023, the group has met on a monthly basis. Initially, one cloud environment for a Heliophysist to work in was envisioned, but it was quickly realized that one environment was not sufficient to satisfy an entire community's needs. To decide on what to include in a few different flavors of environments, the group put together a Google survey form to capture feedback (see Fig 8 for some initial feedback, organized into four separate categories of use cases). In August of 2024, a HelioCloud-based environment prototype was built. Deployments are done with 2i2c¹² (offers scalable and access-controlled Binder/Jupyter resources and recently won a NASA grant to cover compute costs) and ESA Datalabs¹³ (a “public moderated beta” of browser-based tools for scientists with a focus on bringing questions and code to petabytes of ESA data). Thus, there are 3 total deployment options: 2i2c Binder, 2i2c JupyterHub, and ESA Datalabs.

Fig 8: initial meta analysis of Google survey results for Heliophysics environment use cases

Leftover work for this includes finishing gathering survey results, building an environment based on the survey results, making environments citables (e.g., DOIs) for reproducibility, and then releasing this to the broader community, collecting feedback, and iterating as needed. 2i2c also plans to use PyHC as a pivotal use case example of their capabilities.

pyhc-core

pyhc-core¹⁴ is a new PyPI package created by Shawn Polson. This allows one to install the current seven core packages with one pip install command. The package was mostly for a proof-of-concept to show that this idea can work, but currently some issues do exist that prevent it from being used (e.g., Kamodo import fails with Python version 3.12). Eventually, the goal is to have tiered package installs, in accordance with the current plans to create a PyHC package tiering system.

PyHC Docs Hub

pyhc-docs¹⁵ is a readthedocs page that has four of the PyHC core packages documentation information. It supports searching across documentation. This can be useful for finding features across packages and want to read documentation on certain capabilities. There were conversions voiced, however, about this being indexed by search engines (causing issues with people finding the actual documentation itself and avoiding duplication of effort).

PyHC Tech Lead Vision

This part of the presentation covered the things Shawn hopes to see PyHC reach in the next year or two in the unification of PyHC. It is composed of nine components:

1. PyHC environment: access to all PyHC packages in the cloud, next to the data of interest, in a citable format,
2. PyHC Gallery: currently an afterthought, but eventually a display of all package documentation, scraped and in one place,
3. pip/conda installs: pyhc-core package and, eventually, tiered package installs, as well as getting a student intern to help packages move into conda,
4. Linked documentation: the readthedocs work done for the PyHC Docs Hub,
5. Heliophysics Software Search Interface (HSSI): a search interface to more easily discover, find, and access Heliophysics-related software,
6. PyHC summer schools: provide in-personing learning in one big setting, and serve as PyHC's biggest outreach event,
7. PyHC Enhancement Proposals (PHEPs): standards are at the heart of everything PyHC does, and these will help cement that,
8. pyOpenSci - PyHC partnership: helps with quality peer reviews, and

9. PyHC-Chat: with the above 8 components existing, this AI-powered chatbot could leverage all the resources to help scientists do research, write code, write (executable) papers, etc., as well as help developers improve codebases!

Fig 9: A visual representation of the PyHC Tech Lead's vision for a unified PyHC

Heliophysics Software Search Interface

High-level Overview

Presented by the PI (Juile Barnum), the same presentation as given at DASH 2024.

The Heliophysics Software Search Interface (HSSI) aims to fill a gap within software search capabilities in Heliophysics. There are many reasons that this software search interface is needed: 1) generic search interfaces (e.g., GitHub) do not provide science-specific filters to improve search results, 2) ADS's interface links to related software based on software citations, which are still mainly absent in Heliophysics publications, and 3) no current resource adequately helps with software discoverability. Currently, what we already have in Heliophysics isn't sufficient. To begin with, the PyHC search interface only includes Python centric open-source software and lacks software in many categories (e.g., AI/ML, models/simulations). There's also a general need to align metadata structure with Heliophysics' needs and international standards, as well as link out to other important resources (e.g., related software, datasets, etc.).

The HSSI team consists of three teams: 1) the core team with the PI (Julie Barnum), Tech Lead (Shawn Polson), an undergraduate student developer (Isaiah Smith), and a usability testing expert (Jennifer Knuth), 2) the metadata team, consisting of a digital librarian (Catherine Byrd) and an Open Science Expert (Rebecca Ringuette), and the EMAC team of the Leads (Joe Renaud and Eric Lopez), backend developer (Mike Moore) and frontend developer (Dylan Cristy).

The HSSI will unify software metadata with CodeMeta recommendations, improve science software search capabilities, and simplify citation of software in other resources. It will serve as a landing page to search for science software in Heliophysics, starting with the software packages contained within PyHC, and eventually expand out to Heliophysics code in other programming languages. Further, it will strive to include software in other categories (e.g., AI/ML). The HSSI builds upon the design of NASA GSFC's Exoplanet Modeling and Analysis Center (EMAC) software, where our codebase will be directly built from the framework used therein.

Metadata Structure Supporting HSSI and Controlled Vocabularies

This session focused on the metadata portion of the HSSI, with the majority of it focused on gathering feedback on the controlled vocabularies within the HSSI.

The HSSI is relying on CodeMeta recommendations as it is an internationally-used structure for software metadata. Further, it is primarily based on schema.org, which is the structure generic internet search engines use (thus promoting discoverability and findability). CodeMeta has several crosswalks available to many other structures, including GitHub. Lastly, CodeMeta will enable auto-inclusion of HSSI-listed software in a future international software search interface.

The metadata structure for the HSSI will be hosted on GitHub with a RestAPI, routinely archived with Zenodo. For simplicity, development will start with PyHC and EMAC software metadata structures. The metadata structure will apply international recommendations from CodeMeta, Schema.org / Science-on-schema.org, as well as the Research Data Alliance (RDA) FAIR 4 Research Software. This will require mapping from it to other common software structures, including schema.org, Zenodo / DataCite, and GitHub.

With the initial study on what controlled vocabularies are needed, terms are now mapped to CodeMeta, DataCite, and schema.org, with mappings to Mandatory (M), Recommended (R), and Optional (O) terms drafted. The team came up with approximately 30 use cases for the HSSI. From these, it was determined that the HSSI will support citation and basic FAIR, search by programming language, mission/instrument, software relevant to a broad science area, operating system/architecture, application type or functionality, connections to related items (e.g., datasets, publications, other software), and so on. Metadata will be harvested from GitHub (Name, Author, Description, Identifier, License, Programming Language) and Zenodo/DataCite (e.g., related publications, datasets, software, publisher).

Feedback from the PyHC was sourced for application category and software functionality to the end of helping inform metadata structure choices within the HSSI. Both google forms sought to address the following questions: 1) what terms are relevant for Heliophysics, 2) what terms aren't, and 3) what terms are missing? Examples of this feedback are summarized in Figs 10 and 11 below for the application category. The forms were kept open after the meeting to collect as much feedback as possible for incorporation into the HSSI metadata structure.

Fig 10: Responses to “What items in this list describe at least one software package you have developed, contributed to, or used in Heliophysics, whether in Python or not?” for application category

Fig 11: Responses to “What items in this list are not relevant to any software packages you have either developed, contributed to, or used in Heliophysics, whether in Python or not?” for application category

PyHC Tiering Discussion

Currently, two main schools of thought exist for PyHC, both of which have validity:

1. Basic interpretation: PyHC is a collection, and listing, of open-source Python packages with a relevance to Heliophysics and space physics
2. Standards-based interpretation: PyHC strives for compliance with our set standards, package interoperability, and standardization around one or more tools.

The new PyHC package tiering system attempts to unify these two approaches. Older, out-of-date, unmaintained, or publication-specific code could still have a place for listing and findability, while there exists a nuance between other packages that are more robust, trustworthy, maintained, and work toward the standards-based interpretation of being a PyHC package. This way, users can have a solid understanding of what each PyHC package has to offer, and the state of the package’s condition and development. Further, a tiering system will allow for a myriad of benefits at each level.

Ideas for copper, bronze, silver, and gold tier package levels were presented by the PyHC Lead (Julie Barnum), where the tiers go from a basic Python package that’s potentially not open-source, only available as a code repository, etc., to a “cream of the crop” package that has significant interoperability with other PyHC package, installs in a PyHC environment, complies to the highest level with PyHC standards, etc.

Community Ideas for Levels

Following the scene-setting presentation, the community discussed what their vision for each tier should look like in the new tiering system. These thoughts are summarized in the Miro board that everyone worked together on in Fig 12. Overall conclusions were as follows for each tier:

Copper Tier

Many were uncertain about the point of this level (e.g., “wouldn’t this encourage developers to be lazy?”). Further, some wondered about the point of this level existing, as it appeared to mostly be a way for a package to be listed on the site. With the forthcoming arrival of the HSSI, this level felt unnecessary. Some thought that this tier could turn into an “under evaluation” level, which wouldn’t be considered a tier of PyHC. Doing so would allow a package to get “media attention” for its existence, but wouldn’t guarantee a spot within PyHC unless it met the minimum bronze tier requirements.

Bronze Tier

The community recognized that the vast majority of packages would fall under the bronze tier. As for the kind of packages within this level, community members cited the example of a single-maintainer package and/or one that may be slower to respond to issues or questions.

Silver Tier

The community had numerous thoughts for the silver tier. Ideas about installation came up (pip installable, perhaps conda installable as well), license (discussions were had surrounding the potential adoption of an OSI approved open-source license list, minus the NOSA license), stronger standards application (having to comply with all “must” standards and some level of “shoulds”), interoperability with other PyHC packages ramping up, and then a quicker turnaround for developer response rate to questions and pull requests. Although these packages would likely have multiple maintainers, having a large user base likely wouldn’t be necessary to be allowed at the silver tier.

Gold Tier

In general, the community agreed that it would take a little bit for some package to reach this level, and most likely would never reach this point. That being said, the goal for this tier would be high-quality packages, but not so “pie in the sky” that no package could ever reach it. The community discussed the potential for a conda install requirement at this tier, meeting all standards, both “musts” and “shoulds”, a governance structure requirement, and “significant interoperability” with other PyHC packages. Where discussions didn’t fully reach a conclusion was for what “interoperability” exactly means (e.g., is it having common data model adapters, or having the same underlying framework for time, units coordinates).

process to be able to contribute (normal open contributions are not allowed); as such, many deemed it not in the spirit of open-source software. Even if NASA packages don't have a NOSA license, paperwork is still involved in open-sourcing a software package. Perhaps this then could be a point of leverage PyHC could enforce: if a package comes in with a NOSA license, it cannot be a Gold-tier, or even Silver-tier, package. In general, allowing closed-source licenses of any kind were not favored for any package tier, as that would make it by definition not a "community package". Packages as such could be listed instead on the HSSI. Exact details of this requirement will likely be defined in a future PHEP.

DOI

Everyone agreed that a DOI per software version was required for Gold-tier packages, but Silver-tier packages had some variability. In the end, the community decided to have those two tiers be the same, but at the Bronze tier, a DOI for software publication could be allowed.

Standards Compliance

After a lot of discussion on this point, the community decided that each standard PHEP (to be written by Jon Niehof) should define the tier it applies to (or how each tier is defined). That is, if a standard PHEP indicates compliance is needed for a given package tier, then compliance with those "musts" are required, and this will apply to all levels. Thus, granularity is at the PHEP level, and wherever a standard PHEP says "should" or "must" for a tier, a package at this level will meet all "musts" and as many of the "shoulds" as possible. To summarize, packages must comply with all applicable standards.

pyOpenSci-PyHC Review Status

In general, tracking the state of "in progress", etc. is complicated for those approving a package tier. Also, the purpose of the pyOpenSci collaboration would be how PyHC reviews its packages. However, some flexibility might be required since the review requires time, and thus funding (e.g., the SunPy package review in SunPy took awhile itself). The final decisions were: Gold and Silver tiers will have their own separate review processes with pyOpenSci (written in separate PHEPs from this one) and Bronze-tier packages can suffice with a self-review process (must be completed to be a Bronze-tier package). pyOpenSci has thought through this kind of review process far more in depth than anyone in PyHC, and the community will lean on their expertise. Should a future PHEP be instituted that changes, removes, or adds a new standard, the PyHC Tech Lead position will review the packages against that one new standard.

Other requirements

For the other requirements initially included in PHEP 4, the decisions were as follows:

- pip or conda installable: follow the rule determined from the "Standards Compliance" requirement discussion
- PyHC specific environment inclusion: probably not relevant to this PHEP
- Self-evaluation: this was decided to be a Bronze-tier only requirement per the "pyOpenSci-PyHC Review Status" requirement discussion

Further, Day 3 of the PyHC meeting had set aside time for hosting a discussion about some of these exact points, so further discussion was deferred to then. The benefits discussion for each PyHC tier was deferred to the next PyHC telecon in December.

PyHC Package Tiering Specifications

There are four tiers proposed in this PHEP: Copper, Bronze, Silver, and Gold. These would replace the current structure of "Core Packages", "Other Packages", and "Un-evaluated Packages". See the table below for requirements associated with each tier:

	Gold	Silver	Bronze	Copper
Self-Evaluation Status	Completed	Completed	Completed	Not Done
PyHC Standards Grading	Complies with all "must" and many "should" requirements from applicable standards-track PHEPs	Complies with most "must" requirements from applicable standards-track PHEPs	Complies with some "must" requirements from applicable standards-track PHEPs	N/A
pyOpenSci Review Status	Completed	In progress or Completed	Not Started	Not Started
Installable in PyHC environment?	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
HSSI Metadata Compliant?	Silver + some optional fields and controlled vocabulary contribution*	Bronze + all recommended fields*	Copper + some recommended fields*	All mandatory fields*
Software License	Fully compliant, doesn't allow NOSA/GPL license	Fully compliant, allows NOSA/GPL license	Has non-recommended license	Has non open-source license
DOI	Required	Required	Required	Not Required
pip installable?	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
conda installable?	Yes	No	No	No

Fig 13: PHEP 4's current (as of November 2024) ideas for tier-specific requirements

The following table shows the benefits that are associated with each tier:

	Gold	Silver	Bronze	Copper
Summer School Inclusion *	Yes	Yes**	No	No
PyHC-top-tier Env Inclusion *	Yes	Yes **	No	No
PyHC-all Env Inclusion *	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
PyHC-Chat Bot Inclusion *	Yes	Yes **	No	No
Standards Compliance Assistance *	Yes ***	Yes	Yes	Yes
Main Page Listing	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Secondary Page Listing	No	No	No	Yes
HSSI Inclusion	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Conference Travel Funding	Yes	Yes	Yes	No

* = can opt-in or opt-out of this

** = conditional upon justification on importance/use of package (e.g. number of users, level of commitment within PyHC activities, or effort made for those items but gold level not yet achieved)

*** = conditional upon justification that package is in danger of dropping down to a Silver tier

Fig 14: PHEP 4's current (as of November 2024) ideas for tier-specific benefits

Fig 15: Miro board results from the License requirement discussion

Fig 18: Miro board results from the pyOpenSci-PyHC Review Status requirement discussion

PyHC Requirements and the HSSI

Rebecca Ringuette began this session with a quick overview of the HSSI metadata structure, and how it relates to the PyHC tiering discussion. In particular, the software license and DOI are relevant. Within the HSSI, there are three levels of fields: mandatory, recommended, and optional. Mandatory is needed to have a bare minimum operational listing, recommended is needed to generate a complete citation and comply with basic FAIR (also supports buttons on the search interface), and optional serves to improve text search and interlinking (including to the forthcoming helio.data tool). At the time of the presentation, there were 4 mandatory fields, 13 recommended fields, and 11 optional fields. These fields were mapped to various PyHC tiers, where all mandatory fields were deemed Copper level (see Fig 19). Now, of course, these would be Bronze level, based on the earlier decision to remove the Copper tier.

Proposed Distribution of M/R/O for PyHC Tiers

Fig 19: Mapping of HSSI M/R/O fields to PyHC tiers

The group completed a Miro board exercise to give feedback on the HSSI metadata structure. Specifically, Rebecca instructed participants to give feedback on: 1) the package tier associated with a metadata field, 2) terms to be used in a given field, and 3) whether the listed metadata field should support a search button or not. Additionally, feedback on the content of certain controlled lists associated with a metadata field was solicited (e.g., controlled list of various operating systems). The results of the discussion for each tier (plus discussions on optional field not associated with a PyHC tier, and requests for other fields to include) are summarized below in Figs 20-25.

Fig 20: HSSI Metadata and PyHC Copper Tier

Fig 21: HSSI Metadata and PyHC Bronze Tier

Fig 22: HSSI Metadata and PyHC Silver Tier

Fig 23: HSSI Metadata and PyHC Gold Tier

Fig 24: HSSI Metadata Optional fields

Other fields you think should be included (give similar descriptions as done with the tier frames)

Fig 25: HSSI Metadata fields to be included that aren't listed

Interoperability within PyHC

This session, led by Julie Barnum (the PyHC Lead), aimed to organize discussion around interoperability within PyHC. Several factors play into the motivation behind this discussion, including packages' desire for creativity, but also easier collaboration, a need to align dependencies (i.e., within PyHC software environments), decreasing tension in standards between duplication and dependencies, increase PyHC packages' usefulness to the broader user community, and the recent inclusion of PyHC standards in ROSES HTM funding calls. Fig 25 summarizes the sliding scale example of interoperability shown, where in terms of capability one goes from basic interoperability (can install in the same environment as other packages) to "pie in the sky" interoperability (a given task works with software packages in the same science domain as there is a GUI on top of everything), while scope slides from tasks working with software packages in the same science domain, to working with other science domains. Fig 26 shows how Fig 25's fields might map to the different PyHC tiers. The goal of this particular discussion was to put interoperability in the light of package tiering and figure out what interoperability might mean at the different tiers. This approach was taken as it would help integrate the high cost sometimes associated with interoperability, bring in relevant standards, and create an increasing level of commitment to interoperability.

Structuring Interoperability

Example tasks

- Plotting data
- Time/coordinate conversions
- Combine variables using equations, including unit conversions
- Time analyses, e.g. searching for events near other events
- Data processing → ML input
- Complex operations (e.g. fourier analyses)

Fig 25: An example of a sliding scale of software interoperability, considering scope (top) and capability (bottom)

Fig 26: Tiered interoperability Venn diagram

Fig 27 summarizes the interoperability discussion for associating interoperability with the three PyHC tiers for general scope of a package, while Fig 28 shows the same for general capability

of a package. In general, there was the question of “do we raise the ceiling or raise the floor” in terms of the community’s priority for interoperability. Some felt that simply installing in the same environment was too low a bar to even be considered as part of interoperability (i.e., focus on the ceiling), while others pointed out that PyHC can’t currently install all of its packages in the same environment and run all unit tests (i.e., raise the floor). In general, thinking about interoperability in terms of general scope was confusing and led to no specific actionable outcomes. Thinking instead in terms of general capability was much more productive. Different ideas came up for tying the levels in general capability to “real world” examples. They all essentially converged to “how much friction/frustration was involved in getting packages to work together”.

Fig 27: discussion results for PyHC interoperability tiering in terms of general scope

Further, the question was raised as to whether or not PyHC as a whole would like to move towards shared objects as its ideal form of interoperability.? Particularly, given adequate time and funding, would this idea be widely accepted by the community, or is it rather that the community does not want to converge on shared objects at all? Some were in great agreement with the idea, others took a more cautious approach due to issues within subdisciplines of a lack of agreement on coordinate systems (for example), and some outright said they did not want to have common objects. To the last viewpoint, flexibility in choosing the right object for a particular

Fig 28: discussion results for PyHC interoperability tiering in terms of general capability

workflow was preferred over worrying about what inputs are required for the thing they need to call. To summarize, a “be all, end all” object was not desired by the community, but easily passing data around was an attractive option. One way to attack this would be settling on a few common standards to create adapters between.

Reduction in duplication of effort, despite being one of PyHC’s strategic goals, has had little-to-no focus as well. Part of the issue behind the lack of movement here is funding, and another part is likely a fear of defunding work. Moreover, how does the community determine which is the “duplicate”, and thus who is defunded? Some felt as open source projects, we should be inherently working together to make things better; a combination of efforts doesn’t have to mean one individual is out of work, but rather, more people are now concentrating on the same effort. We want to support the research software engineer community as a whole, so bringing people from one project to the next is important, especially considering software generally does have a lifespan (e.g., HelioPy’s sunseting after its period of usefulness declined). The PyHC would greatly benefit from identifying where further areas of collaboration would be useful.

In the end, it was decided that to determine the next steps a PyHC user survey would be helpful. Within the survey, the PyHC could determine where the actual pain points in interoperability are for package users, and potentially what areas of collaboration are missing. This will help the community determine better how to proceed. This was discussed further during Day 3 of the meeting. Secondly, requirements associated with interoperability (i.e., in the package tiers for an individual package) do not make sense with the goals of interoperability. Thus, this will be removed as a requirement in PHEP 4. Third, it was proposed that by the spring

meeting, we should have a repository with CI installing all of PyHC packages into a common environment and running all unit tests. In doing this, we may as a community discover new requirements that the community needs to adopt. Lastly, it was suggested that we as a community step through the summer school materials that focused on multi-package use cases and look at how to improve those areas of interoperability.

PHEP Issues Revisit

In this session, Jon Niehof led discussions on several of the current issues in the PyHC standards GitHub repository. This was mostly an introductory conversation, to the end of assisting Jon in crafting PHEP drafts for the community's consideration. Below are some of the details of each issue:

- Tables in PHEPs¹⁷
 - In PHEP 1, we agreed CommonMark was the widely-adopted, formally specified Markdown variation. However, in PHEP 4, a table was deemed the most appropriate medium for communicating information, and was used.
 - To be decided in the future how we'll officially handle this situation. However it is handled, the end result is that tables will be allowed.
- PyHC standards updates and replacements¹⁸
 - The current standards have not been updated since 2018, and do not have a defined process for update either. This issue suggests a PHEP process for establishing and updating standards. This would begin with writing a set of PHEPs to replace the current PyHC standards. There was general agreement from the community on this approach.
 - In the case of PHEP 3, which will come before the establishment of PHEP 4, the community faces the issues of a standards-track PHEP not specifying what PyHC tier it applies to. In this case, the community agreed that PHEP 4 will have a clause stating that standards-track PHEPs without a specified tier by default apply to the Bronze tier and up.
 - The split for standards track PHEPs were suggested as follows:
 - 1) Community/license standards¹⁹ (capturing the license suggestions from this meeting, requiring a procedure for Code of Conduct violations, etc.)
 - 2) Documentation standards²⁰
 - These could potentially be in the form of “how to’s” instead of “musts”? Though, perhaps what is in our current documentation standard should be firmer (with more musts), and required at the Silver tier and up?
 - 3) Testing and maturity standards²¹ in two parts of “packaging standards” and “development standards” (basically, how to have best practices for development).
 - For development standards, the main difference suggested is to include static analysis in a package’s CI itself. This could be

included in the reference implementation of the PHEP. Code coverage would be great to include in general (ad hoc or in CI).

- As for packaging standards, Scientific Python has a great packaging guide that can be included as a reference. Further, if we're to use pyOpenSci as our way of a review process for Silver and Gold packages, perhaps we adopt their standards for packaging as our own as well? Jon Niehof will look at both and form further discussion for the group. The group also brought up the need to provide extra support to packages struggling with packaging (perhaps as a hackathon session at an upcoming PyHC bi-annual meeting). But it is still worth having this as a standard (and required of all packages) as they're the base level of a functioning Python package.

Next, Nick Murphy presented the idea of an exploratory PHEP for a new package designed for interoperability with `astropy`, `SunPy`, and `PlasmaPy`²². The motivation behind this idea is that there's a significant need for a space physics package that is highly interoperable with `astropy`. The reasoning for that is that in order to be interoperable with `SunPy` and `PlasmaPy`, a package will also need high interoperability with `astropy`. Given that the community agrees this is a need, there are a couple ways forward: 1) modify an existing space physics package (with a major rewrite to rebase code base on `astropy` objects, significant developer time, and likely many breaking changes), or 2) create a new space physics package (design for Particle("Au") interoperability with `astropy`, still requiring a significant time investment, but could act as a front-end to other packages). Either solution requires use cases.

In the end, perhaps a new package is not exactly what's needed, but rather a higher-level data object. The crucial part is that Heliophysicists won't use `AstroPy` if their things aren't in it (e.g. coordinate systems, units, etc). Hence, what happens if we create a package built on `astropy` that has those things in it? Would that make Heliophysicists more likely to use `astropy`? To determine this, we as a community need concrete examples, e.g. python notebooks showing what the analysis looks like now and whether or not that is acceptable for users. Thus, the previously mentioned user survey could become useful. The community agreed in general that this would be a great idea to discover pain points the users are experiencing using PyHC packages, and a prime opportunity to inquire if a Heliophysics package that is built around `astropy` objects would be beneficial. In this case, we would be particularly interested specifically in someone from solar attempting to work on plasma-related research. Some questions to consider: 1) Whether the user is in solar or space physics and 2) where do things fall apart in science workflows, and what doesn't work and/or what creates friction with the current PyHC ecosystem? More details will need to be in the survey. This user survey will be discussed/formulated at the December 16th telecon.

Rebecca Ringuette suggested that we could have a competition at PyHC spring meeting (or the next best PyHC bi-annual meeting) where scientists would present a use case of multiple PyHC packages. Their prize for "winning" would be an afternoon hackathon session where PyHC

developers would work together on how to perform their science work with PyHC packages with the developers in the room. The requirement would be that the presentations would need to focus on cross-disciplinary work, where a scientist bridges remote and in-situ data. We could source participants from the PyHC list, HelioNauts, AGU, summer school students, GEM/CEDAR/SHINE, etc. We could look on ADS/Sci-X for papers that cite/use multiple PyHC packages. HDRL outreach could also help the community with advertising this. Rebecca and Alex Young are both involved with that. Nick also suggested adding a list of publications on the PyHC website that use multiple PyHC packages.

PHEPs 2 and 3 Voting

This session established the second, and final, vote for PHEP 2 (the PHEP template) and the first vote for PHEP 3 (PyHC Python and upstream package support policy).

Per the voting—which happened in Slack—**PHEP 2 passed its second vote**. 12 total PyHC members were involved in the voting. Those who voted yea are: Julie Barnum, Nick Murphy, Rebecca Ringuette, Stuart Mumford, Shawn Polson, Brent Smith, Darren De Zeeuw, Jim Lewis, Jon Vandegriff, Will Barnes, and Nabil Freij. Jonathan Smith abstained from voting. Having passed its second vote, PHEP 2 is now approved for merge.

PHEP 3 essentially recommends the adoption of SPEC 0, as well as the new addition of support for new versions of the indicated dependencies within 6 months of their release. This PHEP will replace the current standard 11 in the PyHC standards document. The standards document will be updated after a successful passing of PHEP 3 to point to it. There was some pushback that the “shoulds” should be musts, and it should have a note that it applied to the Silver tier and up (however, PHEP 4 technically doesn’t exist yet). In the end, the group decided the PHEP is fine as is for now. However, in the future it will likely be applied as “shoulds” for the Bronze tier and “musts” for the Silver tier and up (directly within PHEP 4). Per the voting—which happened in Slack—**PHEP 3 passed its first vote**. 13 total PyHC members were involved in the voting. Those who voted yea are: Julie Barnum, Nick Murphy, Rebecca Ringuette, Stuart Mumford, Shawn Polson, Brent Smith, Darren De Zeeuw, Jim Lewis, Jon Vandegriff, Will Barnes, and Nabil Freij. Jonathan Smith and Alex Young abstained from voting.

A general note that in the future, PHEP votes should take place at the beginning of the meeting to capture a wider sampling of community voices. Further, voting for PHEPs will be on GitHub in the future for easier tracking (and a public record). They could be comments or explicit approval within the PR itself.

Next Steps

No hackathon session was held at the end of the meeting due to a lack of topics. The next PyHC meeting is set to be held sometime in May (more information to come after the holidays

on that). This will be held as a hybrid meeting once again, and switch all future Fall meetings to virtual-only to alleviate some travel stress. Following telecon topics will be:

- November 18: finish out PHEP4 miro board
- December 2: licenses discussion (to the end of drafting a PHEP)
- December 16: user survey creation

The 2025 telecon series will start up on January 13th.

Based on the discussions within this meeting, there will also be several updates made to the metadata efforts for the HSSI, changes to PHEPs in progress, and several new PHEPs written to better flesh out the current PyHC standards.

References

- ¹ <https://hapi-server.org/servers/>
- ² <https://packaging-guide.openastronomy.org>
- ³ <https://pyspedas.readthedocs.io>
- ⁴ <https://chiantipy.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>
- ⁵ <https://github.com/wtbarnes/fiasco>
- ⁶ <https://fiasco.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>
- ⁷ <https://github.com/jeplowman/EMToolKit>
- ⁸ https://github.com/medley56/space_packet_parser
- ⁹ <https://space-packet-parser.readthedocs.io/en/stable/index.html>
- ¹⁰ <https://github.com/radiation-belts/rbamlib>
- ¹¹ <https://rbamlib.readthedocs.io>
- ¹² <https://2i2c.org>
- ¹³ <https://datalabs.esa.int>
- ¹⁴ <https://github.com/heliophysicsPy/pyhc-core>
- ¹⁵ <https://github.com/heliophysicsPy/pyhc-docs>
- ¹⁶ <https://github.com/heliophysicsPy/standards/pull/31>
- ¹⁷ <https://github.com/heliophysicsPy/standards/issues/38>
- ¹⁸ <https://github.com/heliophysicsPy/standards/issues/39>
- ¹⁹ <https://github.com/heliophysicsPy/standards/issues/33>
- ²⁰ <https://github.com/heliophysicsPy/standards/issues/34>
- ²¹ <https://github.com/heliophysicsPy/standards/issues/35>
- ²² <https://github.com/heliophysicsPy/standards/issues/40>

Final agenda

Start Time (MT)	End Time (MT)	Title	Presenter/Discussion Lead
Monday, Nov 11			
9:15	9:15	Introductions, welcome, meeting goals	Julie B.
9:15	9:15	<i>HAPI</i>	Bob W or Jon V
9:15	9:15	<i>PlasmaPy</i>	Nick M.
9:15	9:15	<i>SunPy</i>	Stuart M.
9:15	9:15	<i>SpacePy</i>	Jon N.
9:15	9:15	<i>pysat</i>	Jonathon S.
9:15	9:15	Break	
9:15	9:15	<i>Kamodo</i>	Darren D.Z.
9:15	9:15	<i>PySPEDAS</i>	Jim L.
9:15	9:15	<i>CLEDB Introduction</i>	Alin P.
9:15	9:15	Lunch	
9:15	9:15	<i>fiasco</i>	Will B.
9:15	9:15	<i>EMToolKit DEM Framework</i>	Joe P.
9:15	9:15	<i>Space Packet Parser</i>	Gavin M.
9:15	9:15	<i>Radiation Belts Analysis and Modeling Library in Python</i>	Sasha D.
9:15	9:15	<i>Science Platforms Coordination/pyhc-core</i>	Shawn P.
9:15	9:15	Break	
9:15	9:15	HSSI High-Level Overview	Julie B.
9:15	9:15	Metadata Structure supporting HSSI and Controlled Vocabularies <i>software category/functionality and mission vocab</i>	Catherine B.
		<i>Feedback</i>	Joe R., Catherine B., Rebecca R.
Tuesday, Nov 12			
9:00	9:00	<i>Broad Strokes for PyHC Tiers</i>	
		<i>Topic Introduction</i>	Julie B.
		<i>Community Ideas for Levels</i>	Julie B. (and Rebecca R. as assisting moderator)
9:00	9:00	Break	
9:00	9:00	<i>Tier Requirements / Tier Benefits</i>	Julie B. (and Rebecca R. as assisting moderator)
9:00	9:00	Lunch	
9:00	9:00	PyHC Requirements and the HSSI	
		Overview requirements associated with each PyHC tier	Rebecca R.
		<i>Feedback</i>	Rebecca R., Joe R., Catherine B., Julie B.
9:00	9:00	Break	
9:00	9:00	Interoperability within PyHC	Julie B.
		<i>Scene Setting Presentation</i>	Julie B.
		<i>Discussion - lots of it</i>	
18:00		Group Dinner at Rio Grande Boulder (1101 Walnut St, Boulder, CO 80302)	
Wednesday, Nov 13			
9:00	9:00	PHEP issues revisit	
		CommonMark in PHEPs Revisit	Jon Niehof
		Standards Document Revamp: summary of standards-track PHEPs	Jon Niehof
9:00	9:00	Short Break	
9:00	9:00	Exploratory PHEP on new space physics package	Nick Murphy
9:00	9:00	Short Break	
9:00	9:00	PHEP voting (PHEPs 2 and 3)	Shawn P (Jon N. out)
9:00	9:00	Wrap Up	Julie B
Optional Hackathon Afternoon			
12:00	12:00	Hacking Session (Optional)	